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Evaluation of Extended Projected Profiles impact on vertical trajectory prediction

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Abstract. The future Air Traffic Management System (ATM) is based on the concept of Trajectory Based Operations (TBO), in which all stakeholders have access to a consistent and synchronised view of flight trajectories. In the TBO framework, the trajectory prediction plays a key role. Inaccuracy of current trajectory predictors caused by the lack of a common understanding of stakeholders' intents can be reduced by the sharing of information by airspace users. A step towards a shared information network is the Extended Projected Profile (EPP), downlinked from airborne to ground via automatic dependent surveillance contract (ADS-C). In summary, it contains the flight intent from the Flight Management System (FMS) and other information. This paper explores the EPP messages and the possible performance enhancement they introduce in the predictions of the top of descent (TOD) and the descent vertical profile. ¹

1. Introduction

The future TBO framework requests the use of synchronised trajectories, available for all stakeholders. In the current ATM system, neither the information possessed by each actor nor their intents is transparent for the others. The lack of information sharing hinders synchronisation [1].

A step forward to the future ATM system is progressing sharing of airborne EPP information to the ground via ADS-C, revealing previously unknown variables for a better trajectory prediction by ground trajectory prediction engines, including mass or speed profiles [2].

EPP messages contains the flight intent and other information obtained from the FMS and are downlinked to ground systems via ADS-C [2].

The availability of airborne information allows the adjustments of the ground estimated flight intent and improve the trajectory prediction.

EPP exploitation is still in a research stage [3]. The content is sensitive data for airlines, and few aircraft are currently equipped for sharing this information and, therefore, it only can be exploited for research purposes.

Given the challenge of trajectory prediction in the descent phase due to the uncertainty on the TOD position [4] and the different aircraft guidance mode, this paper focuses on a set of flights for a descent

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flow of analysis selected from the Spanish Pamplona Upper sector (LECMPAU), where the data sample has 58 flights, including real traffic data and EPP messages.

The objective of this paper is to evaluate the discrepancy between the EPP and actual flight trajectory, the evolution of the EPP intent and the benefits EPP information could bring to ground-based trajectory prediction.

The dataset of analysis is composed by surveillance information and the EPP messages of 58 flights that belong to a descent flow in LECMPAU with southbound traffic, destination Adolfo Suárez Madrid–Barajas Airport (LEMD).

2. Extended projected profile

For each flight of equipped aircraft with a contract in place, EPP messages are reported continuously, updating the current flight state and local conditions. The data includes:

- location, current gross mass, guidance modes, flight level, ground track, speed, actual heading, speed, wind, and temperature etc.

and offering the reference trajectory at the report moment from FMS:

- estimated level, speed, and time etc.

The reference trajectory contains only a segment ahead the current position. This paper targets a tactical environment. Therefore, to analyse the benefits EPP may bring, the main objects of analyses are the last report before entering to the sector of analysis (msg_0) and the subsequent messages before reaching the real TOD (msg_1 , msg_2 , etc).

3. Preparation and method

The analysis is arc-length-based (see Figure 1) [5] [6]. The distance from the entry point to the sector along the central trajectory of the flow until the position of TOD is the γ_{TOD} . This paper considers the coordinates of the point where the vertical speed starts to change as the TOD. A flight could have several starts of the descent if it performs a stepped descent. In this case, the TOD is referring to the last one.

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3.1 Data preparation

The EPP message provides most of variables necessary for the analysis. Some actions and transformations were needed to obtain the final sample of analysis:

- Identification of msg_0 .
- Identification of the messages from msg_0 to the last message before TOD.
- Calculation of the planned TOD from FMS of each message ($\hat{\gamma}_{TOD,0}$, $\hat{\gamma}_{TOD,1}$, $\hat{\gamma}_{TOD,2}$...). The TOD's coordinates are directly given, indicated by a bit string (10101000).

3.2 Method

The aim is to explore the predicted vertical profile of FMS and to evaluate the impact of new variables in improvements on a ground prediction of TOD based on historical data (baseline).

The variables selected from the radar tracks for training TOD ground predictors are:

- FL_0 : flight level at the entry of the sector.
- V_0 : ground speed at the entry.
- WV: wake vortex of the aircraft.
- ADES RWY: runway configuration of the destination airport.

The variables selected from the EPP for the analysis are:

- Reference trajectory: including the vertical profiles and the associated location of TOD, as well as their variation through the messages (from msg_0 until the message before TOD).
- Current gross mass ($m_{0,0}$) and predicted mass at TOD ($\hat{m}_{TOD,0}$) of msg_0 : the relationship between mass and TOD location is analysed.
- Vertical guidance mode (Vmng): the relationship between the guidance and TOD location is analysed.

Apart from the predicted vertical profile, the rest of the variables will be used to train TOD EPP-informed classifiers to evaluate their impact on the position of the TOD.

To obtain comparable results, baseline and EPP-informed classifiers are trained to predict the TOD interval (I_{TOD}) instead of γ_{TOD} , by considering equidistant distance interval since the entry of the sector (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. Arc-length-based TOD location and interval.

The machine learning (ML) algorithm used for the training is eXtreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost), a supervised learning algorithm capable of providing reasonable performance with small data sample [7].

The results will later be compared to the $\hat{I}_{TOD,0}$.

The metrics of evaluation are:

- Number of true positives (TrP)
- Number of predictions with 1 interval of deviation (sDev)
- Root-mean-square deviation (RMSE)

4. Results

4.1 TOD location

The location of the TOD is key for the ground trajectory prediction systems to predict the vertical profile of the flights, as it directly impacts on the aircraft descent profile.

(a) $\hat{\gamma}_{TOD,0}$

Figure 3 shows the location of the TOD according to msg_0 . The red scatter is the real TOD extracted from radar tracks and the blue one is the TOD obtained from the EPP reference trajectory.

As the traffic belongs to a north-south flow, all flights are expected to – according to the reference trajectories – start the descent mainly on the second half of the trajectory. Most of the flight would have descended within a similar TOD range.

However, some of the flights descend earlier in the first half. None of the analysed EPP msg_0 captures these behaviours.

Figure 2. \hat{I}_{TOD} of EPP messages.

Figure 3. TOD location according to msg_0 and radar track.

(b) $\hat{\gamma}_{TOD}$ and its variation

In the analysis sample, the maximum number of messages after msg_0 and before TOD is 3 (msg_1, msg_2 and msg_3).

Figure 2 presents the actual γ_{TOD} and the $\hat{\gamma}_{TOD}$ given by the EPP messages. Each line represents one flight and the point the corresponding distance to TOD. The range of γ is split into 7 intervals of 15 nautical miles (NM) to visualise the I_{TOD} of the flights.

The early descents ($I_{TOD} = 1, 2, 3$) present large deviation with $\hat{\gamma}_{TOD,0}$. While flights that descended at $I_{TOD} \geq 4$ are mostly located in the same interval as $\hat{\gamma}_{TOD,0}$ or in the two surrounding intervals.

Regarding the variation though the series of report, the reference TOD reported is similar for most flights. Variation takes place when the message is reported after the descent or slightly before.

The largest difference between $\hat{\gamma}_{TOD,0}$ and $\hat{\gamma}_{TOD,1}$ is 10.29 NM of a double steps descent, because the msg_1 is reported after the first descent and the vertical segment remains the same. The same happens between $\hat{\gamma}_{TOD,1}$ and $\hat{\gamma}_{TOD,2}$.

Figure 4. Examples of vertical profile with variation after descent (left) and slightly before descent (right).

(c) Variables impact in I_{TOD} classifiers

This subsection presents the performance analysis of the classifiers trained with different combinations of inputs (FL_0 , V_0 , $\hat{I}_{TOD,0}$, $\hat{Y}_{TOD,0}$, m_0 , $\hat{m}_{TOD,0}$, WV, Vmng and ADES RWY).

The sample of analysis is not balanced, the most frequent output (I_{TOD}) is 4, 5 and 6. Hence, if the inputs are not relevant, the prediction will be concentrated on these intervals.

Table 1. Analysis sample - number of flights per I_{TOD} .

I_{TOD}	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
N° flights	4	2	1	12	19	16	4

The sample is split into train (46 flights) and test sample (12 flights).

The performance of the classifiers is presented on Figure 5 and summarised on Table 2. One of the flights in the test sample has $I_{TOD} = 1$ (example presented in Figure 6), it has relevant effect on the RMSE, therefore a reference to evaluate the impact of the inputs. It will be referred as $f_{I=1}$ for simplicity.

In the classifiers of one input, decision trees try to identify the range of values of the input for each possible output.

The training sample size does not fulfil the dataset size requirement for large number of input variables, and any combination with more than 2 inputs gives same or worse results. Therefore, among the combinations including more than one input, Table 2 summarise only conclusions for relevant two inputs classifiers.

The table also includes $\hat{I}_{TOD,0}$ of the msg_0 for comparison.

The main deviation of the predictions comes from the early descent caused by external factors such as conflict avoidance and regulation.

Among the baseline classifiers, the classifiers of WV, Vmng and ADES RWY are not sufficiently trained, they always provide the same output because of the imbalance of the train sample and the similarity between the inputs. These variables are mainly *Medium*, *True* and *North Configuration*, respectively. However, the performance is good due to the imbalance in the test sample.

From the EPP variables, $\hat{I}_{TOD,0}$ classifier provides major TrP than the baselines and $\hat{Y}_{TOD,0}$ model has the lowest RMSE among the single input classifiers although it does not present major number of TrP. The low RMSE of the latter is caused by the less deviated prediction of $f_{I=1}$. Hence, the use of ML classifier enables the prediction of early descent.

By combining baseline and EPP inputs, the performance is further improved. The classifier with lowest RMSE is trained with $\hat{I}_{TOD,0} - \hat{m}_{TOD,0}$. And $FL_0 - \hat{I}_{TOD,0}$ has the highest number of TrP.

On the other hand, the TOD given by the reference trajectories of EPP, $\hat{I}_{TOD,0}$, outperforms the single-input trained classifiers, including the one trained with $\hat{I}_{TOD,0}$, with 4 TrP and 6 predictions with deviation of 1 interval. However, as presented in previous section, the early descents due to unexpected events are not captured.

Figure 5. EPP XGBoost classifiers' test confusion matrix.

Table 2. Characteristics of classifiers trained with more than 1 input and $\hat{I}_{TOD,0}$.

Detail	Input	N° TrP	N° sDev	RMSE	Comments
Classifiers	$FL_0 - V_0/$ $FL_0 - \hat{I}_{TOD,0}/$ $V_0 - m_0/$ $V_0 - \hat{m}_{TOD,0}$	1/5/2/1	5/3/6/6	5.17/ 5.08/ 5.0/ 5.33	Predicts $\hat{I}_{TOD} = 1$ for an instance of $I_{TOD} = 6$.
	$\hat{I}_{TOD,0} - m_0/$ $\hat{I}_{TOD,0} - \hat{m}_{TOD,0}/$ $\hat{Y}_{TOD,0} - m_0$ $\hat{Y}_{TOD,0} - \hat{m}_{TOD,0}/$	4/4/4/2	4/3/6/6	1.83/ 1.58/ 1.58/ 3.75	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Predicts $f_{I=1} (I_{TOD} = 1)$ correctly. Low RMSE.
$\hat{I}_{TOD,0}$	-	4	6	3.33	Small difference to the real descent for most cases, the early descents are unpredictable.

4.2 Variation of vertical profile

Based on the match of the TOD and the descent segment, the sample could be split into ten categories, each category represents a possible situation.

When the descent segment is the only unmatched part (e.g., category III), it could be caused by the variation of the speed profile. While the discrepancy of TOD could be due to:

- ATFM regulation, such as ATC Capacity.
- Safety assurance measure to avoid interaction between the flights. It could involve possible use of opposite direction level (ODL).

Figure 6 shows an example of category VII. The red line represents the actual profile, the flight present triple steps descent with a cruising segment at ODL, FL360.

The early descent along with the use of ODL are ATC measures to avoid potential conflicts with other two flights cruising at FL370 and FL350, whose trajectories interact with the selected flight.

The EPP message reported when the flight was located at the ODL, msg_1 , is similar to msg_0 . It does not consider the fact that the use of ODL should be avoided, and the flight has to return to an odd flight level as soon as possible. Otherwise, if another flight in opposite direction is present, the use of FL360 could induce a potential conflict.

Figure 6. Example of vertical profile variation of category VII.

5. Conclusion

In summary, the EPP reference vertical profiles matches with the actual ones when the flight does not present interdependency with others. When the flight is issued a FL change clearance to avoid potential conflicts or to facilitate the traffic management in high-density scenarios, the EPP message is unable to anticipate this change. The discrepancy of the intention between controllers and pilots will cause deviation on the estimated and the real vertical profile.

Although in the EPP reported after the manoeuvre, the information will be updated. In these cases, the TOD location might present large variation with respect the previous report. Otherwise, the variation is usually neglectable.

For the ground trajectory predictors, the vertical prediction could be improved with the use of the mass variable and the EPP TOD interval ($\hat{I}_{TOD,0} - \hat{m}_0$ or $\hat{I}_{TOD,0} - \hat{m}_{TOD,0}$).

Future lines for the research may include larger sample of analysis, studying the behaviour of the EPP in other operating environments and for other phases of flight such as climb.

Once there is a large number of EPP data that can be actually traced to surveillance data, EPP data can be used to explore the sensitivity of the ground trajectory predictor depending on different variables such as Guidance Mode and Mass. Also, the dependency of weather and how TPs can be improved by using these data online can be featured in a future research paper.

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